

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis showed that the complexes have a ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 giving MLI (M=Ni or Co) composition. The formula suggested that the moniodo complexes formed contained metal ions in the 3+ oxidation state and were presumably five-coordinate.

The molecular weights show that the complexes are monomeric. Thus the Schiff bases behave as tetradentate dibasic ligands as is known. The iodine seems to occupy the fifth coordination site giving five-coordinate Ni(III) and Co(III) complexes. The low conductivity of all the complexes in acetone confirms the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The room temperature magnetic moments (Guoy method, $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant, corrected for diamagnetism) of all Ni(III) complexes are 1.78-1.81 B.M. values close to the spin-only moment for one unpaired electron. Such values are known⁹ for Ni(III) complexes. The result is such as might be expected for the spin-paired configuration $b_{2g}^2 e_g^4 a_{1g}^1$. The room temperature magnetic moments of all the Co(III) complexes are found to be in the 0.5-0.6 B.M. range. This seems to be due to T.I.P.^{10,11}.

The ir spectra of the complexes showed the absence of the OH stretching band at $\sim 3600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ observed in the ligands suggesting its deprotonation for the purpose of complex formation. The M-O stretching band is observed at $\sim 440 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ^{12,13}. A band at $\sim 515 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ^{12,13} is considered to be due to M-N bond. The bands at 1620 cm^{-1} found in the ligands are found at $1580-1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ¹⁴ in the complexes, thereby suggesting the C=N group participation in coordination to the metal atom. A clear band in the far ir at $189-192 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ¹⁵ in these complexes is assigned to M-I stretching vibration.

Thus the complexes are apparently five-coordinate and presumably square-pyramidal, with one iodide out of plane of the rest of the molecule, and may be considered to have C_{4v} symmetry so that Ni(III) complex has 2A_1 and the Co(III) 1A_1 ground states.

The electronic spectra of the Ni(III) complexes in acetone exhibit bands around 400 and 505 nm which are also present in the ligands. Three more ill-defined weak bands are also observed around 560 ($\epsilon=240$), 680 ($\epsilon=86.80$) and 830 nm ($\epsilon=60$) in all Ni(II) complexes. The last two bands may be assigned to $^2A_1 \rightarrow ^2B_1$ and $^2A_1 \rightarrow ^2E$ transitions. The band at 560 nm seems to be a charge transfer one.

The electronic spectra of the Co(III) complexes in acetone exhibit the intra-ligand bands around 400 and 505 nm. Three other bands are obtained at 630 ($\epsilon=420$), 685 ($\epsilon=265$) and 830 nm ($\epsilon=88$) in all the complexes which could be assigned to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$; d_{yz} , $d_{xz} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$; d_{xz} , $d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transitions.

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Polarographic Determination of Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of the Complexes of Praseodymium(III) with Hydroxylamine, Hydrazine and Phenylhydrazine

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IN continuation of our previous work on the complexation study of cerium(III)¹ and neodymium(III)² with hydroxylamine, hydrazine and phenylhydrazine the present study on the complexes of praseodymium(III) with the same ligands is reported.

Experimental

A.R. grade chemicals were used to prepare all the solutions. The solutions of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, hydrazine hydrochloride and phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (Chroma, Germany) were

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF 1 : 1 COMPLEXES OF Pr(III) WITH HYDRAZINE, HYDROXYLAMINE AND PHENYLHYDRAZINE ($\mu=1.0 M KCl$)

	log K		ΔH kcal/mole for difference of 10°	ΔG kcal/mole		ΔS cal/degree/mole	
	25°	35°		25°	35°	25°	35°
Hydrazine	3.4	3.0	-17.8	-4.7	-4.2	-43.9	-44.3
Hydroxylamine	3.1	2.9	-10.5	-4.2	-4.1	-21.1	-21.1
Phenylhydrazine	3.0	2.6	-13.1	-4.1	-3.7	-30.3	-30.3

prepared in double distilled water. The metal solution was prepared by dissolving the metal oxide in minimum hydrochloric acid and was standardized with EDTA³.

In the test electrolytic solutions, the concentration of Pr(III), potassium chloride and gelation was 2.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01%, respectively. Ligand concentration was varied from 1.0 to 10.0 mM in each case. Ionic strength was maintained with potassium chloride at 1.0 M. Sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid were used to adjust the pH of the test electrolytic solutions at 2.40 ± 0.02 .

Polarograms were recorded on an automatic pen recording polarograph (C.I.C., Baroda). The capillary used had a m' value of 2.15 mg/sec and drop time of 3.10 sec/drop at 44.0 cm effective height of mercury. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the solution for deoxygenation. Elico digital pH meter (Model LI-120) was used to measure the pH of the test electrolytic solutions.

Results and Discussion

Pr(III) gives a well defined reversible three electron reduction wave at pH 2.40²⁻⁵ in 1.0 M potassium chloride with 0.01% gelation used as a maximum suppressor. The log plot slopes come to the order of 20 ± 1 mV for Pr(III) and its complexes with all the three ligands indicating reversibility of the electrode process. The waves for metal ion and its complexes were found to be diffusion controlled as revealed from the straight line plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} , the reduction of Pr(III) at pH 2.40 \pm 0.02 was -1.81 V vs SCE. The half-wave potential shifted to more negative values on increasing the concentration of ligand. Lingane's⁶ method has been used to determine the composition and stability of complexes (Table 1). Thermodynamic parameters (Table 1) were calculated from the well known thermodynamic relations⁷. The order of stability constants of the complexes is $[Pr(C_6H_5NHNH_2)]^{3+} < [Pr(NH_2OH)]^{3+} < [Pr(NH_2NH_2)]^{3+}$.

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Thermal Stability of *m*-Xylene-formaldehyde Resin and Its Derivative

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LITERATURE¹⁻³ reveals that products resulting from nitration and chlorination of a resin had better thermal stability than the parent resin. There was dramatic increase in char yield and a decrease in maximum rate of weight loss for nitro-substituted system compared to their non-nitrated analogues². It was therefore believed that the substitution on a polymer backbone played an important role in the thermal stability. In the present work, the derivatives of *m*-xylene-formaldehyde resins were prepared and their thermal behaviour studied.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of analytical grade. *m*-Xylene-formaldehyde (*m*-XF) resin was prepared using *m*-xylene and paraformaldehyde with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid as catalyst⁴. The experimental conditions for nitration and chlorination of *m*-XF resin were the same as those of *p*-XF resin³. The experimental details for characterization of the samples are the same as reported earlier³.